

On the way to a configurable testbed to support IoT research

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Abstract

The progress in Edge computing, along with the rapid uptake of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, is driving research across various domains that encompass well-known subjects such as Cyber-Physical Systems, Smart Environments, Digital Transformation, Industry 4.0, and others. However, despite the considerable focus from the scientific community and governmental funding directed towards these areas, researchers consistently confront a pivotal question: how can they create realistic testbeds that effectively validate the solutions being examined without allocating substantial portions of their research budgets?

Currently, scientific communities are engaged in the design and implementation of distributed research infrastructures aimed at assisting researchers in their experiments and assessments. In this document, we introduce our concept of a platform intended to offer a distributed infrastructure that supports researchers working on the Internet of Things (IoT). To achieve this, we utilize techniques such as containerization, network I/O virtualization, and Sensing and Actuation-as-a-Service (SAaaS), all of which are features provided by the I/Ocloud paradigm, a solution that leverages the open-source IoT middleware Stack4Things.

Edge Computing, IoT, I/Ocloud, SAaaS, Virtualization, Containerization

1 Introduction

The previous decade has seen significant attention from researchers towards computing paradigms driven by the emergence of Cloud Computing. Additionally, advancements in microchip manufacturing processes have resulted in more robust devices, and with the rise of IoT devices, paradigms such as Fog, Edge, and Continuum Computing have gained prominence in computing research.

Among these, Edge computing stands out as a fundamental component in various prominent research areas, including Cyber-Physical Systems, Intelligent Transportation Systems, and Continuous Machine Learning. A major challenge faced by researchers in the Edge computing domain is the establishment of a realistic testbed to evaluate and validate the effectiveness of their research. Preparing such a testbed is a task that demands a considerable investment of both the researcher's time and financial resources, ultimately hindering overall productivity. Moreover, these testbeds are specifically designed to cater to the needs of the research or projects at hand. Although they can be modified for other research purposes, such adaptations require even greater investments of energy, time, and money.

In recent years, several initiatives launched by the government aim to provide usable testbeds to meet the needs of researchers, to mention a few: FIWARE [1], Chameleon [2], Fed4FIRE+ [3], IoT Lab [4], F-Interop [5], and SLICES project [6]. These initiatives are designed to offer open, accessible, and dependable facilities that support a diverse array of research activities. Fed4FIRE+ provides a federation of Next Generation Internet (NGI) testbeds. This initiative is strengthened by the integration of infrastructures that are specialized in the Internet of Things (IoT), as provided by the IoT Lab. Their facilities are utilized by F-Interop, a Horizon 2020 European research project that aims to integrate and enhance several European testbed federations to research and develop online testing tools for the Internet of Things. Additionally, the SLICES project specifically aims to establish the first-ever European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Research Infrastructure (RI) to support research in Digital Sciences. Moreover, SLICES aspires to create a Europe-wide testing platform that offers advanced computing, storage, and networking components, all interconnected through dedicated high-speed links. This platform is intended to serve as the primary collaborative tool for researchers across Europe, enabling them to explore and advance the future of the Internet.

At the same time, commercial products are available with their services, such as Amazon AWS¹ and Google², to mention the two most prominent players in the market. All the previously mentioned initiatives concentrate on providing Cloud-based facilities that can only partially meet the primary needs of an Edge-computing researcher, and even more so for an Internet of Things (IoT) researcher: testing applications across the Edge and IoT (which primarily consist of constrained devices) distributed over a specific area and, in certain instances, interacting with physical devices, either directly or through mediation. To elucidate this concept, the outcomes derived from tests conducted on ad-hoc or cloud-based testbeds invariably exhibit limitations due to their inherent characteristics. In the former scenario, this is due to the lack of concurrent access to the testbed resources (multi-tenancy management), while in the latter, it stems from the necessity to emulate the devices or, at the very least, the devices that are connected to them.

Creating a platform designed to facilitate IoT-based systems for experimental research is a challenging task. It must provide essential characteristics that establish the infrastructure: i) dynamically configurable, ii) programmable, iii) able to run in parallel multiple assignments and

¹<https://aws.amazon.com/?nc2=hlg>

²<https://cloud.google.com/>

tests by preserving the isolation of the execution environments running on it, and iv) lastly but not less relevant, the infrastructure has to provide an environment that is geographically dispersed as it could be the actual application environment (i.e., Smart City and Cyber-Physical Systems, or Intelligent Transportation Systems).

The initial two characteristics represent two facets of the same concept. They provide the flexibility of the infrastructure utilized by a researcher from the perspective of infrastructure management (dynamic configuration, such as network setup or available features) and from the computational tasks executed on Edge and IoT devices (programmability, for instance, a Machine Learning model or a straightforward function). The third characteristic is essential, as the assumption of solely utilizing the resources is minimal in a practical context and must be factored into the evaluation of research outcomes. By design, a platform is capable of executing multiple tasks while ensuring the isolation of the execution environment (i.e., through containerization). Lastly, another characteristic is the geographical distribution of the testbed components established by a researcher. Indeed, an application or solution operating on the IoT is intended to function within a specific geographical area (whether extensive or limited); thus, factors such as network latencies or instability must be taken into account during testing and assessment.

This paper provides a comprehensive overview of our platform, which is designed to facilitate research in the Internet of Things (IoT). The overview examines its key functionalities, which are part of the Stack4Things and I/O cloud solutions. Additionally, a dissertation discussing various use cases implemented on the platform is included at the conclusion. We believe this work is significant in supporting initiatives that aim to establish infrastructure for researchers' endeavors, such as SLICES[6], Fed4FIRE+[3], IoT Lab[4], and F-Interop[5]. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the scenario in which this work is conceived and introduces the two solutions based on this work. Sections 3 and 4 present the main aspects that have to be managed by the investigated scenario. Section 5 presents two use cases in which the utilization of a platform as the one discussed can simplify the testbed setup, increasing our productivity. Consideration and next steps are discussed in Section 6.

2 Background

Cloud Computing is instrumental in expanding the benefits of computing, storage, and networking capabilities to applications. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) definition of Cloud computing [7] describes a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services). As per the definition provided by NIST, these resources can be quickly provisioned and released with minimal management effort and without the need for the service provider's involvement. Consequently, the Cloud paradigm offers a dual advantage: users have the freedom to manage their resources, while providers can prevent resource wastage (such as the computational power of servers being idle or only partially utilized). If the preceding statements outline advantages for a resource provider, they equally apply to an industry or company that can

enhance its revenue by leveraging Cloud computing. The advantages offered by the Cloud have pushed the research to produce advancements in: i) management (e.g., service models: IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS [7]), ii) resource usage accounting [8], iii) resource optimization provisioning [9, 10], and iv) resource aggregation patterns (e.g., Federation or Multi-Cloud approaches [11], to mention a few. In this wave, several products are proposed as Cloud management systems, for business or research purposes, freeware or not, such as AWS Cloud¹, Google Cloud computing², Microsoft Azure³, and OpenStack [12]. The latter specifically refers to a collection of open-source software tools designed for the construction and administration of Cloud computing platforms. OpenStack serves as a Cloud solution suitable for various commercial, in-house, and hybrid deployments, providing a completely open-source ecosystem of tools and frameworks that facilitate the management of virtualized computing and storage resources in accordance with the principles of the Cloud paradigm.

The extensive utilization of Internet of Things (IoT) devices enhances research on Cloud computing methodologies, broadening the focus of resource management to encompass the network edges. In fact, IoT devices operate at the network's edge and offer a multitude of devices equipped with sensing and actuating functionalities, serving as programmable gateways to the physical realm.

Generally, the majority of methods aimed at fully leveraging the IoT ecosystem predominantly depend on embracing the Cloud paradigm to deliver data-centric solutions such as [13, 14], where the operations allowed are solely those related to data manipulation. The improvement of this prior approach provides comprehensive control over an IoT infrastructure and facilitates the re-programming of it. Consequently, users can choose vertical solutions to implement and oversee their infrastructure. Commercial solutions are currently available in the market. (e.g., AWS Greengrass⁴ or IBM Watson IoT⁵) alongside open-source and research products such as OpenIoT[15] or Stack4Things (S4T)[16].

However, a comparable solution does not allow application developers to share an IoT infrastructure. Consequently, each user must establish their own infrastructure, which poses a limitation for the widespread adoption of IoT applications, as the capital expenditure associated with IoT infrastructure is frequently significant. Furthermore, obtaining authorizations for the deployment of IoT nodes in public areas for extensive implementations can be quite challenging. Alongside the restrictions on sharing the IoT infrastructure, data-centric solutions typically rely on transmitting all generated data to a datacenter (or a Cloud provider). For example, an IoT sensing deployment with numerous sensors generating data at a high rate can lead to considerable operational costs related to bandwidth [17], storage, and processing cost. In these situations, it may be advantageous to process the generated data at the edge and send only the pre-processed information to the Cloud, thereby minimizing high bandwidth and storage consumption. Conversely, processing data at the network edge is also beneficial for meeting the demands of standard time-sensitive applications that cannot afford delays caused by relying on a distant Cloud.

³<https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/>

⁴<https://aws.amazon.com/greengrass/>

⁵<https://www.ibm.com/cloud/internet-of-things>

2.1 Stack4Things

Stack4Things seeks to address the challenges posed by data-centric solutions for managing IoT devices. It is an open-source middleware that is part of the OpenStack ecosystem, designed to facilitate the management of IoT (or Edge device) deployments. S4T endeavors to provide appropriate functionalities for IoT infrastructure to integrate with an edge-extended IaaS Cloud. Fig. 1 shows the OpenStack subsystems involved in the S4T IoT management, introducing IoTronic, a subsystem meant for the provisioning and configuration of IoT nodes with hosted sensing and actuation resources. Regarding the remaining components of the OpenStack subsystem utilized in S4T, the networking service known as Neutron has been improved to facilitate network connectivity for IoT nodes positioned at the network edge. Additionally, to present the resources of the edge-based IoT nodes as Web resources, we employed the OpenStack Designate subsystem to link publicly resolvable domain names with the distributed physical and virtual IoT nodes, even when they are deployed within IPv4 masquerade networks.

Figure 1: Stack4Things subsystems.

Stack4Things middleware has an architecture composed mainly of two parts: a Cloud-side component (IoTronic) and one (or multiple) edge-side component(s) (Lightning-Rod), as shown in Fig. 2.

IoTronic is designed in accordance with the standard architecture of OpenStack services to guarantee its complete compatibility with other OpenStack subsystems (for instance, Keystone, Neutron, Designate, Qining, etc.). By design, the Edge nodes that are to be managed through S4T are regarded as (embedded) smart devices that can support a minimal Linux distribution (for example, OpenWRT) such as Single Board Computers (SBCs) (e.g., Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and

Figure 2: Stack4Things architecture overview.

Arancino⁶) that are microprocessor (MPU)-powered. For this reason, Lightning-Rod (LR) is designed as a lean agent modular and fault-tolerant adapt to this category of devices. LR serves as a crucial element in the S4T architecture, connecting Edge devices to the S4T IoTronic service, even when these devices are situated behind NATs or stringent firewalls. The implementation of Web-Socket, facilitated by the Web Application Messaging Protocol (WAMP), enables the establishment of a full-duplex messaging channel between the Cloud and the devices, effectively allowing for the routing of traffic streams, such as commands. The communication channels established in this manner are ideally suited to the constraints of Edge and IoT devices, leveraging two key features: publish/subscribe (pub/sub) messaging and Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs).

2.2 I/Ocloud

The I/Ocloud approach [18], leverages the functionalities of S4T to provide standardized and generic programming capabilities that operate on IoT resources, irrespective of the configurations of the underlying infrastructure. Furthermore, this methodology retains the capacity to utilize the distinctive features of an IoT-enhanced distributed datacenter, including the availability of edge nodes, which can subsequently serve as computing infrastructure for data (pre)processing. Con-

⁶<https://smartme.io/projects/arancino-cc/>

sequently, this methodology seeks to facilitate a seamless integration between Cloud and IoT by offering distributed IoT resources (i.e., sensors and actuators) that are hosted on nodes situated at the network edge as virtualized Cloud resources. This integration is a pivotal aspect of the I/Ocloud: it must guarantee that IoT deployments function as active components of the Cloud infrastructure while maintaining their inherent characteristics. In conclusion, it is essential to ensure effective I/O virtualization (virtIO).

Figure 3: I/Ocloud operational view

As shown in Fig.3, I/Ocloud broadens the virtualization concept into the realm of IoT by abstracting IoT resources and presenting them as virtual entities that can be accessed through a developer-friendly interface, corresponding to an I/O primitive of their physical equivalents. The abstraction mechanism is programmable: it can apply to all I/O resources of an IoT node or merely a portion of those resources, and it can also logically consolidate IoT resources from various IoT nodes into a single (logical) entity.

The I/O Virtualization, shown in Fig. 4, is based on filesystem virtualization⁷ to offer a vir-

⁷Linux-based IoT boards leverage a GPIO pseudo-filesystem to interact with physical pins

Figure 4: I/Ocloud virtualization approach.

tual depiction of the pins of a physical IoT node while simultaneously hosting user-defined logic and facilitating interactions with remote physical IoT resources. From a technical perspective, an I/Ocloud instance constitutes a self-sufficient and isolated environment featuring a user-defined file system, *sysfs* realized with the exploitation of *FUSE*[19] technology over Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs) to ensure remote interactions with the physical IoT resources.

3 Virtualization and Isolation facilities

The I/Ocloud solution, utilizing the capabilities of I/O virtualization, is able to provide users with one or more instances of Virtual Nodes (VNs). A VN can be created as a standalone and portable environment (for instance, a lightweight container) either within the Cloud datacenter or at a distant Edge (or IoT) node, as it is shown in Fig. 4. Thereby, some benefits are so obtained:

- Application logic requesting great computational resources (or relying on data-centric approaches) running on a VM (or on a lightweight container) on the Cloud can accede to multiple resources and data exploiting I/O virtualization;
- Application logic that suffers latency issues can be distributed and run over the Edge nodes;
- It is possible to realize and test business logic, both centralized and decentralized, as desired;

- It is possible to migrate or replicate VNs from Cloud to Edge and vice-versa.

I/Ocloud exploits the OS-level virtualization [20], more commonly known as containerization, as a solution for I/O virtualization and VN management. Indeed, this virtualization approach, rather than dedicating a whole OS for each guest VM, enables multiple isolated user-space environments (namely the container) to run on a single host machine while sharing a unique kernel provided by the host. A container has its own dedicated resources, such as file systems, TCP/IP stacks, to name a few. Due to the constrained nature of Edge and IoT devices and a limited demand of computing resources (as well as in terms of storage for the images [21]) the containers are the best solution for the VN virtualization, especially if advanced functionalities (e.g., container migration) may be put in place [22]. Nevertheless, the containerization enables the VN isolation; the I/O Hypervisor grants access to the VNs requesting to interact with the physical resources, as shown in Fig. 4.

4 Networking Facilities

The virtualization of IoT nodes and their physical resources alone is insufficient to achieve a fully configurable testbed on Edge and IoT devices; to accomplish this objective, I/Ocloud requires a mechanism to also facilitate network virtualization. In this context, networking capabilities and network virtualization are essential, particularly when each component may be obscured by networking barriers, as is the case in Edge or IoT deployments. The I/Ocloud view is designed to allow users to create customized networking topologies that can include any combination of Virtual Machines (VMs) and Virtual Networks (VNs) across both the datacenter and Wide Area Networks (WANs), particularly when VNs are deployed at the network edge (see yellow dashed lines in Fig. 3). Networking management is achieved through the integration of Neutron capabilities and the connectivity between IoTronic and Lightning Rod. This connectivity involves channels that link the Cloud to Edge devices by utilizing S4T-bound mechanisms, which include Websockets and reverse tunneling. Thereby, the I/Ocloud can exploit the Neutron mechanisms to set up virtual LANs by leveraging the Neutron abstractions of *network*, *subnet*, and *port*. In particular, the *network* abstraction is used to isolate the operative context to provide the multi-tenancy management of infrastructure. Furthermore, in our approach, the *binding* hosts (where Neutron ports are established) are situated within the same machines that house the WS tunnel agents (see a red dashed rectangle in Fig. 5). This decision was intentional, as the WS agents are capable of establishing WS tunnels to connect Neutron ports created on those machines to the IoT nodes positioned at the network edge via WebSocket. In simpler terms, ports are generated and managed in the Cloud and subsequently linked to the IoT nodes located at the network edge through WebSocket in a distinct two-step process.

As shown in Fig. 6, which represents the S4T node-side architecture, attaching an IoT node to a virtual user-defined network is relatively straightforward. Specifically, a Virtual Interface (VIF) is created on the IoT node and subsequently linked (via a reverse WebSocket tunnel) to the OpenStack networking platform overseen by Neutron in the Cloud.

Figure 5: Integration between S4T and Neutron facilities Cloud-side.

Figure 6: Integration between S4T and Neutron facilities IoT-side.

5 Use Cases

In this section, we provide several examples of research where utilizing a platform to establish a testbed could have greatly accelerated our efforts. One of the most appropriate use cases to il-

illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed platform is the Smart City scenario, where replicating a realistic city-scale testbed is challenging, unless certain a priori assumptions are made. A Smart City represents an ecosystem of infrastructure and services designed to integrate society, government, and technology to deliver improved services (such as smart mobility and smart environment). This comprehensive perspective necessitates a holistic approach to adopting technologies and services, thereby offering a wider (or even global) solution to urban challenges. In this context, there is a requirement for a scalable architecture that focuses on reusing, multiplexing, and sharing technologies and services at the urban level. The objective is to create a cohesive ecosystem where various applications can expand to a metropolitan scale, thereby supporting an open and shared Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) infrastructure composed of sensing, actuation, networking, processing, and storage resources. As done in the TOO(L)SMART [23] project, five Italian cities have shared an ecosystem-oriented template based on sensing and actuation devices. The system can be expanded and tailored through the control logic operating in the Cloud. In particular, the objective is twofold: firstly, to deliver a consistent representation of interconnected smart objects by abstracting, categorizing, and managing them as a cohesive ecosystem of smart objects that can be configured, personalized, and contextualized in accordance with high-level application needs. Secondly, there is a necessity for a management layer that can oversee the dynamics of the ecosystem, translate these high-level requirements into more granular ones, and establish and enforce specific policies to meet these needs. Consequently, a viable solution may involve adopting a software-defined methodology, wherein fundamental mechanisms provided by smart city objects at the data plane are utilized by the control plane to enforce policies pertaining to application or end-user requirements. Therefore, we refer to this concept as Software Defined Cities.(SDCs) [24].

The testbed for this scenario, constructed using the platform under analysis, can be implemented with data-plane level components operating on IoT devices. One or more Virtual Networks (VNs) are executed in the form of containers that are capable of interacting with sensors and actuators. Conversely, control-layer components can operate in the Cloud as virtual boards (see Fig. 7).

In the same scenario, research about realizing an infrastructure dynamically configurable upon a Software-Defined City is more complex than the previous one. Fig. 8 depicts the architectural schema in which multiple domains (three environments divided by vertical dashed lines) cooperate through federation. The elements of the domain infrastructure are categorized into three distinct layers (namely, physical, data, and control layer) each possessing different computational resources. All domains are federated, and the configuration is not distributed. In accordance with the principles of the platform, the testbed can be established with ease contrary to our earlier research, which necessitated the establishment of multiple independent OpenStack clouds and the virtualization of various components in the form of virtual machines. In fact, by utilizing I/Ocloud and Neutron virtual networking, it becomes feasible to establish three distinct networks among a collection of devices. The services of the Control Layer can be made accessible through Stack4Things (or via Designate, depending on the testing strategy). The inter-domain tunnel can be evaluated in a realistic context, taking into account the pool of geographically dispersed IoT devices.

Figure 7: Software-Defined City.

Figure 8: High Level architecture of Software Defined City [25]

6 Conclusions and Future Work

This work has outlined the fundamental concepts and mechanisms that facilitate the development of a platform capable of creating on-demand IoT and Edge computing testbeds, serving as a robust

tool to assist researchers in their investigations.

In contrast to other initiatives that provide testbeds and facilities for researchers, the framework introduced here does not simply grant access to federated, geographically distributed IoT testbeds (as exemplified by IoT Lab). It also offers complete programmability of the devices, enabling researchers to tailor device behavior, abstract functionalities, and effectively separate application logic from device-management logic.

All of the aforementioned elements form the initial yet substantial foundation for a comprehensive platform that already incorporates the essential functionalities necessary for experimental studies in this field.

Additional features would undoubtedly enhance such a platform (for instance, Function-as-a-Service support). Nevertheless, the next significant step will indeed involve the definition and implementation of a fully realized Testbed-as-a-Service (TaaS) offering specifically designed for IoT researchers who require a flexible and powerful tool to investigate and validate a diverse range of designs.

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